

Assessing the System Learning Organization Model in the Petroleum Development and Engineering Companies

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Abstract

The research is performed for evaluating the System Learning Organization Model in the Petroleum Engineering and Development Company, a subsidiary of National Iranian Oil Company. The Statistical Population in research center was 80 staff with education (M.A and PH.D), using random sampling, with the sample volume was extracted from Morgan table which showed 66 required samples. The research method is from the type of applied and also description/survey. The tool for gathering data was questionnaire and its validity was measured through content method and its reliability via Cranach's coefficient alpha %93 was confirmed. Collected data were analyzed by SPSS software and using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. binomial test analysis shows that the situation "learning dynamics, organizational transformation, knowledge management, technology application" in the Petroleum Engineering and Development Company was in accordance with system learning organization model but "people empowerment" was not in accordance with the systematic model.

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Keywords: Learning Organization, learning dynamics, organizational transformation, knowledge management, technology application.

1. Introduction

The development of any society is possible only with the advancement of education and research institutions in that society. Since the Petroleum Engineering and Development Company as a knowledge-based organization have significant value and strategic importance in the development of oil fields, Therefore, this model of learning for managers and employees of these organizations will be more beneficial in achieving competitive advantage in the national and international levels.

This system can be developed with the participation and cooperation of the mind, and to make changes that will affect the whole system.

Accordingly this study intends Michael Marquardt learning organization model system in 1391 to study Petroleum Engineering and Development Company. This model consists of five subsystems, "learning", "organization", "people", "science" and "technology" which is dynamically linked and complements each other, and as an open system, the equipment and infrastructure of the learning organization are considered.

As the arm of Petroleum Engineering and Development Company - Research - National Iranian Oil Company in the field of executive development projects, missions, manage and monitor the implementation of all projects in development, engineering and design activities, engineering, construction and implementation of the National Iranian Oil Company and related services to them is responsible. (A documentary article 3 Petroleum Engineering and Development company)

Since such a device with at least one step in a knowledge-based approach of knowledge - science - technology and behavior patterns is ahead of other institutions

So one of the important mechanisms to increase productivity and development of the device is the establishment of learning process.

Accordingly, the researcher is seeking to investigate Characteristics of learning organization model system in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company; it is obvious that the first step to achieve this is to identify the current status of the organization.

The main objective of the study was to assess the Petroleum Engineering and Development Company in terms of "learning organization" model (SLOM).

2. Materials and Methods:

According to evaluation of the results of the various models of learning organizations and organizational learning capabilities, we can see that a system of this model over other models is its advantage, Because of the many variables and other characteristics of the other models used in this model.

The main research question was whether the state oil company and the development of "learning organization" are based on the learning organization model?

The main hypothesis of this research is based on "the Situation in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company in terms of" learning organization "is based on the system model of learning organization."

In The minor hypothesis of Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's compliance status in terms of "active learning", "organizational change", "empowerment", "knowledge management" and "use of technology" in the learning organization model, was addressed.

Thematic scope of the present study is to evaluate the learning organization model system in the Petroleum Engineering and Development Company. Realm of space research is in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company. The study started 90 of 20 February 1391 and ended in January month.

The aim of the present study is a part of applied research. The study sample of 80 staff with postgraduate and PhD in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company form. We use simple random sampling method and sample size is 66 person based on Morgan chart. Data from the present study consists of two parts, library studies and research.

We use Cranach's alpha to determine the reliability of this study. Using a preliminary sample ($n = 30$) for the total scale Cranach's alpha coefficient equal to 0/933, which indicates the reliability of the questionnaire is high.

To test the hypothesis of binomial distribution, nonparametric tests were used. Variable measuring Marquardt learning organization questionnaire includes 10 questions, 5 choices for the dynamic study, 9 questions for organizational change, to empower people 7 questions, 10 questions for the knowledge management and 7 questions for application technology. Each of these dimensions has several components and majored based on Likert scale.

2.1 Results:

The average of each of the elements of a learning organization suggests that:

Average dynamic learning with a mean (3/91) have most compatibility with operating systems model of learning organization and empowering people with mean (2/95) minimum compliance with the system model in learning organization.

The first hypothesis of the "Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's situation in terms of" active learning" isn't based on a learning organization system model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/000>. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. And because the P value is lower than α , so the null hypothesis is rejected.

Since the observed ratio is larger than the ratio test (0/98> 0/50) the current situation in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company in terms of "active learning" learning organization is based on a system model.

In examining the second hypothesis Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of "organizational change" isn't based on learning organization system model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/019. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

In examining the third hypothesis Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of "empowering people" isn't based on learning organization system model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/175. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. So the null hypothesis is accepted.

In examining the 4th hypothesis Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of "knowledge management" isn't based on learning organization system model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/001. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

In examining the 5th hypothesis Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of "using technology" isn't based on learning organization system model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/000. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

At the end in examining the main hypothesis of this research: "the Situation in Petroleum Engineering and Development Company in terms of" learning organization "isn't based on the system model of learning organization." model (h0). Binomial test P value is 0/000. **That is tested** in the = 0/05. So the null hypothesis is rejected.

2.2 Discussion:

Based on the results and achievements of research, proposals can be express for managers and employees of Petroleum Engineering and Development Company, based on the stated criteria. The proposed dynamic learning go training managers and employees of "adaptive learning" to "prospective learn" to move forward in this way ant expand their knowledge. Management system paid more attention on system of thought that underlies the theory of learning organization And to describe the events they depict a comprehensive system model And understand the relationship between needs and goals, and the total units of the organization And pay attention to the impact their decisions have on the outside of the organization.

In Part Organizational Transformation, The part that corporate culture change that cost seeking the knowledge and problem-solving, Relevance of learning design and development prospects, Objectives and institutional mission, Management commitment and full support of innovative and creative activities, Have a shared vision that is supported by all staff, Directors welcomed the changes and challenges in the creation of a flexible organizational structure is proposed.

The topic of empowering individuals, managers executive with a sense of empathy, attunement and collaboration between members, the spirit of teamwork in organizations to institutionalize, And compensation system for the team's success, individual success is drawing separately, Managers and staff help each other grow and learn and solve problems in activities.

Staff is empowered to identify and find new solutions, to create a corporate culture with an emphasis on open dialogue and create safe space sanctity substrates suitable for the practical application of learned skills is provided.

In the discussion of knowledge management to enhance organizational learning, knowledge management systems must lead to knowledge dissemination.

Employees who knowledge based must be used.

Technological tools such as collaboration tools, knowledge bases, tools, document management systems, intelligent systems, and so it goes. Finally, technological systems should be coordinated with the needs of users

2.3 Conclusions:

Since the study was conducted in a government organization, performing such research in public and private organizations, different results can be obtained. the differences can be realized by studding The results of a comparative between government agencies, public and private companies, There are several factors that have been identified as key elements of a learning organization, but in this study, only five of the learning organization model system was tested, Other researchers are suggested to other key elements of a learning organization and organizational learning to investigate.

Comprehensive system model and the standard model, but can be added to other components and variables can be used again.

As the other suggestion, each component and how to improve them in various organizations can be study.

Because the idea of implementing a learning organization, depending on the research that will improve and expand the components of a learning organization

3. Tables

Table 1: The results of binaminal hypotesis tests

Result	α	p-value	Ratio	Hypothesis	Number of Hypothesis
accepted	0/05	0/000	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's situation in terms of" active learning " is based on a learning organization system model	1
accepted	0/05	0/019	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of " organizational change " is based on learning organization system model	2
rejected	0/05	0/175	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of " empowering people " is based on learning organization system model	3
accepted	0/05	0/001	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of " knowledge management " is based on learning organization system model	4
accepted	0/05	0/000	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company's position in terms of " using technology " is based on learning organization system model	5
accepted	0/05	0/000	0/50	Petroleum Engineering and Development Company in terms of" learning organization "is based on the system model of learning organization	the main hypothesis

4. Figures

The main reason for the use of the learning organization model in this study is more comprehensive than the other models. Figure 1 shows the current analytical framework.

Figure (1): conceptual model (Marquardt, 2002: 24)

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